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“MOMENTUM ON ICE”

A figure skater dressed in baby blue skating attire looked lovely and ready to compete in the Olympics Figure Skating. Elijah stepped onto the rink, a sharp steel digging into the frozen surface with a screeching sound. A low friction between her skates and the ice that allows her to push off the ice and propel herself to glide easily and smoothly. Elijah waved at her parents excitedly and said good luck to her.

Her interest in figure skating began when she witnessed her mother compete in the Olympics and won a gold medal. She remembered how beautifully her mother moved on the ice the first time she saw her. Gliding, jumping, and spinning seemed simple.

'She chuckled and thought 'It wasn't that simple.'

But look at her now; exactly like her mother, she moved so effortlessly on the ice. She generates linear momentum by crouching forward in the direction of motion to keep her balance while accelerating. As she prepares to perform one of the most difficult jumps in figure skating, the Quad Axel.

During takeoff, Elijah used force against the ice to propel herself upward, creating the first lift required for leaps. While in the air, she exploited angular momentum to rotate, allowing her to perform multiple spins and accelerating by pulling in her limbs to reduce her moment of inertia, showcasing her body control. As she prepares to land, she bends her knees to absorb the impact while maintaining her balance, landing backward on the opposite foot to complete the jump successfully.

The national anthem was scarcely audible over the chanting of Elijah's name. She won her first gold medal in Olympics Figure Skating. She thanked her mother for introducing her to figure skating and, she thanked her father for a better understanding of figure skating given that he is a physics professor.

Elijah and her father agreed: "Well, figure skating is physics."